

The Reconciliation Approaches of al-Shāfi'ī and al-Ṭahāwī in Resolving Contradictory Ḥadīth Concerning Udhiya (Sacrificial Meat)

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: April 20, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: November 24, 2021</p> <p>Keywords : Contradictory Ḥadīth, Reconciliation, Sacrificial Meat, al-Shāfi'ī, al-Ṭahāwī.</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5725222</p>	<p><i>Some of the Ḥadīths seem to be against one another and create confusion. Early Muslim theologians, al-Shāfi'ī (d204/820) and al-Ṭahāwī (d321/933) have discussed this issue in their books Ikhtilāf al-Ḥadīth & Sharah M'āni al-Athār and derived rules in the light of Qur'an and Sunnah to resolve contradiction. There are contradictory Ḥadīths about the usage of sacrificed animal's meat after three days of Sacrifice (Eid-al-Adhḥa). Both the theologians have discussed them in their books. The objective of this article is to highlight the approaches and methodologies used by them to resolve contradiction regarding the Ḥadīths about the matter. For this purpose, the approaches of both scholars have been comparatively analyzed. Both scholars agreed that sacrificial meat can be eaten after three days of sacrifice but they differ with each other about the status of the contradictory Ḥadīths. According to al-Shāfi'ī the forbidding from storing the sacrificed animal's meat after three days was not mandatory but it was optional. So, the rulings not to store the sacrificial meat were not to be followed compulsorily. But according to al-Ṭahāwī there are two positions of these Ḥadīths. The ban on eating the sacrificial meat after three days was only to inspire the people for charity and there is no any problem to use it after three days. But if the purpose of forbidding was to declare it Harām (prohibited) after three days, then this ruling is abrogated.</i></p>

Introduction

In addition to the Qurān, the other major sacred source of guidance is the Sunnah, the practices and examples of the Prophet Muhammad's life that have been transferred to the next generations through *Ḥadīth*. The Prophetic tradition which describes the saying, deed and tacit approval of the Prophet (peace and blessings be upon him) is called *Ḥadīth*. Moreover, the sayings and religious acts of the companions of the Prophet are considered *Athār*. The Prophet (peace and blessings be upon him) gave so many instructions to the people during his life. He also decided many issues of the people. He (peace and blessings be upon him) introduced a lot of changes in life gradually. Sometimes, we find some contradictions in the sayings and deeds of the Prophet (peace and blessings be upon him). The Prophet (peace and blessings be upon him) forbade the people from doing an act, afterwards, he allowed them. For example, the Prophet Muhammad (peace and blessings be upon him) said, "I have forbidden you to visit the graves, now you are allowed to do so." But sometimes, we get confused to know that he had done an act in three different ways. For example, we find three different *Ḥadīths* in which the Prophet (peace and blessings be upon him) made ablution (Wudhu) by washing some of the organs of his body once, twice and thrice. The Muslim scholars of *Ḥadīth* discussed this issue and derived different principles from the *Ḥadīths*, to address this problem. Different books have been compiled which discuss this issue but the books of al-Shāfi'ī (d204/820) and al-Ṭahāwī (d321/933) are the earlier one in this field.

In this article, the issue of eating the sacrificial meat after three days of sacrifice has been selected from their books *Ikhtilāf al-Ḥadīth* by al-Shāfi'ī and *Sharah M'āni al-Athār* by al-Ṭahāwī. This issue has been discussed, analyzed and compared. The reason of selecting the topic is that it contains contradictory *Ḥadīths* on which the rules derived from *Ḥadīths* can be applied easily.

1. The Issue of Using Udhiya (Sacrificial Meat) after Third Day of Sacrifice

To slaughter a particular animal on the Festival of Sacrifice (*Eid-al-Adhḥa*) by a Muslim who has financial power, is called Sacrifice. It is one of the signs of Allah according to the Qurān. "So, pray unto thy Lord and slaughter the sacrificed animal." The concept of sacrifice is found in all the main religions of the world with minor difference. It is not a new practice, it started in early age of Prophet Adam. The main purpose of the sacrifice is to provide the opportunity of getting meat for the poor who are not able to purchase it. But there are different *Ḥadīths* in the books of *Ḥadīth* about the eating or giving the sacrificial meat in charity. Both al-Shāfi'ī and al-Ṭahāwī are agreed as well as disagreed upon the issue and have used their principles to resolve contradiction in the *Ḥadīths*.

2.1 Al-Shāfi'ī's Approach

For how long may we eat the sacrificial meat? There are *Hadīths* which show that it can be used maximum for three days but some of them show that the Prophet (peace and blessings be upon him) consumed it for more than three days. This issue has been discussed under the chapter Meat of Sacrificed Animal (لحوم الضحايا) in *al-Shāfi'ī's* book *Ikhṭilāf al-Ḥadīth*. Three *Hadīths* and two verses have been quoted to explain the matter by *al-Shāfi'ī*. Besides, he has also described how to distribute the sacrificial meat among the relatives and the poor.

First *Hadīth* in which the Prophet forbade eating the meat of sacrificed animal for more than three days and later on allowed, has been reported by *Jabir ibn 'Abdullāh* in the book of *al-Shāfi'ī* as under;

حَدَّثَنَا الرَّبِيعُ، قَالَ: أَخْبَرَنَا الشَّافِعِيُّ، قَالَ: أَخْبَرَنَا مَالِكٌ، عَنْ أَبِي الزُّبَيْرِ، عَنْ جَابِرِ بْنِ عَبْدِ اللَّهِ، أَنَّ رَسُولَ اللَّهِ صَلَّى اللَّهُ عَلَيْهِ وَسَلَّمَ نَهَى عَنْ أَكْلِ لَحْمِ الضَّحَايَا بَعْدَ ثَلَاثِ، ثُمَّ قَالَ بَعْدَ ذَلِكَ: «كُلُوا، وَتَزَوَّدُوا، وَأَخْرُوا»

It was narrated to us by al-Rabī' (d 217/832) he said al-Shāfi'ī told us that Mālik told us from Abi Zubayr from Jabir ibn 'Abdullah that the messenger of Allah forbade eating the meat of the victims after three days (of sacrifice) and later on he said, "Eat, give in charity and store."

The second *Hadīth* that has been narrated by *'Abdullāh ibn Waqid ibn 'Abdullāh* about the matter as follow;

حَدَّثَنَا الرَّبِيعُ، قَالَ: أَخْبَرَنَا الشَّافِعِيُّ، قَالَ: أَخْبَرَنَا مَالِكٌ، عَنْ عَبْدِ اللَّهِ بْنِ وَاقِدِ بْنِ عَبْدِ اللَّهِ أَنَّهُ قَالَ: «نَهَى رَسُولُ اللَّهِ صَلَّى اللَّهُ عَلَيْهِ وَسَلَّمَ عَنْ أَكْلِ لَحْمِ الضَّحَايَا بَعْدَ ثَلَاثِ»

It was narrated to us by al-Rabī' he said al-Shāfi'ī told us that Mālik told us from 'Abdullāh ibn Waqid ibn 'Abdullāh who says, "Apostle of Allah forbade eating the meat of victims after three days (of sacrifice)."

It can be noticed that in first narration reported by *Jabir ibn 'Abdullah*, the both orders have been described about the sacrificial meat, but in the second, only ruling of forbidding has been described that meat cannot be consumed after three days. After that *al-Shāfi'ī* also quoted that *'Abdullah ibn Abī Bakar* mentioned about eating the sacrificial meat after three days of sacrifice before *'Amara (bint Abd-ur-Rehman)* and she said,

I have heard 'Ayesha while saying that a group of people from village attended the festival of sacrifice in the era of the Messenger of Allah (peace and blessings of Allah be upon him) who said, "Save one third, and give the rest of in charity." When it was, they said to the Messenger of Allah (peace and blessings of Allah be upon him): O Messenger of Allah! People were benefiting from their victims, and getting fat from them and making water skins, said the Messenger of Allah (peace and blessings be upon him): "Then what?" or as he said - they said: O Messenger of Allah!, "You forbade eating the meat of the victims after three days. The Messenger of Allah (peace and blessings of Allah be upon him) said: "I had forbidden you because of the group (of people) that had come in the days of sacrifice (for meat) now you may eat, give in charity and preserve (it is up to you).

It means when there was a need to distribute the meat among the poor people who had come from villages, the Prophet forbade storing the meat for more than three days and when there were no people who needed it, he allowed to store and eat it according to their wish.

Al-Shāfi'ī conciliates these *Hadīths* by saying that to forbid eating the sacrificial meat after three days by the Prophet, was not in mandatory sense for the Muslims, it was optional. It was temporary for the situation prevailed on the particular occasion. That was the reason, when the Prophet (peace and blessings of Allah be upon him) was asked about the matter he allowed to use it according to the wish of every one, whether he wants to eat, give in charity or store for coming days. To support his view point, *al-Shāfi'ī* argues with the verses of the Qurān, in which the orders have not been used in mandatory sense. Allah says in the Qurān, "When they (animals) fall down (after slaughter), eat of them and feed (the poor)."

According to *al-Shāfi'ī*, the ruling of eating and feeding the meat of sacrificial animal, in this verse is not on mandatory basis, it is optional. Besides, it is allowed to eat the meat of one's own sacrificed animal if the sacrifice is optional (*nafl*) and not mandatory. And the Prophet (peace and blessings be upon him) ate the meat of his own sacrificed animal because it was optional (*nafl*) not mandatory. So, if the sacrifice is mandatory for a man, it is not allowed to eat it by self, he will have to give the whole of it to the needy and poor. It is same as *zakāt* that cannot be utilized by self. For example, when it is mandatory for someone to give some particular amount of his money as alms (*zakāt*) and he spends some of it for his own benefit, he is defaulter, he will have to pay the whole amount. *Al-Shāfi'ī* has quoted verse of the Qurān to explain that when the sacrifice is not mandatory even then its meat should be given to the poor and needy.

He (*al-Shāfi'ī*) also described the best way to distribute the meat of sacrificed animals. One third part of sacrificial meat can be used by self, one third should be given as gift and one third in charity. It is preferable and ideal way, not compulsory one. If the people have problem of shortage of food, the ruling of the Prophet about forbidding eating the meat after three days should be followed and the meat should not be stored for more than three days of sacrifice.

Al-Shāfi'ī further claims that if anybody does not give the poor the meat of his optional sacrifice, he mistakes but he will not have to revise his sacrifice. However, he should give some other thing to a needy if he

comes to him even after the days of sacrifice. If anybody slaughters his sacrificial animal before the time of sacrifice, he will have to slaughter another one as sacrifice.

2.1.1 Analysis of al-Shāfi'ī's views

It is now clear that *al-Shāfi'ī* has not counted these *Hadīths* in abrogation but the situation is like abrogation, because the Messenger of Allah, Muhammad first forbade eating the meat of sacrificed animals after three days of sacrifice and later on, allowed to use it according to one's wish. It can also be derived that he considers the sacrifice as an optional practice not mandatory because the man who sacrifices can eat its meat, but if it is mandatory, he cannot. On the other hand, *al-Shāfi'ī* claims that if anybody slaughters his sacrificial animal before the time of sacrifice, he will have to revise it. The question arises, if it is not mandatory why is it necessary to revise it?

2.2 Al-Taḥāwī's Approaches

Al-Taḥāwī also discussed this issue under the chapter "To Eat Sacrificial Meat after three days of sacrifice (اكلحوم الاضاحى بعد ثلاثة ايام) in his book *M'āni al-Athār*. He has narrated four *Hadīths* which describe the prohibition of eating the sacrificial meat after three days of sacrifice and three *Hadīths* that describe the practice of eating of that meat after three days by the Prophet Muhammad (peace and blessings of Allah be upon him). Then he argued that there is possibility of abrogation in these *Hadīths*. So, he narrated eight *Hadīths* that showed the abrogation of ruling of forbidding eating sacrificial meat after three days of sacrifice. After that he raised an objection about the *Hadīth* reported by Ali ibn Abi Talib (d40/661) and clarified. At the end he narrated the sayings of Ayesha and concluded that there are two aspects of the ruling for not preserving the sacrificial meat after three days. If the ruling of forbidding was only for the inspiration of the people, it is alright and if the order was to make it *Harām* to eat and preserve then it would be counted in abrogation.

First *al-Taḥāwī* narrated the *Hadīths* in which it is forbidden to eat sacrificial meat after three days of sacrifice as follows;

حَدَّثَنَا أَحْمَدُ بْنُ دَاوُدَ، قَالَ، ثنا يَعْقُوبُ بْنُ حُمَيْدٍ، قَالَ: ثنا عَبْدُ الرَّزَّاقِ، عَنْ مَعْمَرٍ، عَنِ الرَّهْرِيِّ، عَنْ أَبِي عُبَيْدٍ، مَوْلَى عَبْدِ الرَّحْمَنِ، أَنَّهُ سَمِعَ عَلِيَّ بْنَ أَبِي طَالِبٍ، رَضِيَ اللَّهُ عَنْهُ يَقُولُ يَوْمَ الْأَضْحَى: «أَيُّهَا النَّاسُ، إِنَّ النَّبِيَّ صَلَّى اللَّهُ عَلَيْهِ وَسَلَّمَ قَدْ نَهَى أَنْ تَأْكُلُوا نُسُكَكُمْ بَعْدَ ثَلَاثٍ، فَلَا تَأْكُلُوهَا بَعْدَهَا»

It was reported to us by Ahmad ibn Daud, he said, it was reported to us by Yāqoob ibn Humayd, he said, it was reported to us by Abd al-Razzāq from Ma'mar from al-Zuhari from Abi Ubaid moula Abd al-Rehman that he listened Ali ibn Abi Tlib said on the day of sacrifice, "O people the Prophet (PBUH) forbade eating the sacrificed animal after three days. So, don't eat after that."

Then *al-Taḥāwī* narrated another *Hadīth*

حَدَّثَنَا ابْنُ أَبِي دَاوُدَ، قَالَ: ثنا أَبُو صَالِحٍ، قَالَ: حَدَّثَنِي اللَّيْثُ، قَالَ: حَدَّثَنِي عُقَيْلٌ، عَنِ ابْنِ شِهَابٍ، قَالَ: حَدَّثَنِي أَبُو عُبَيْدٍ، مَوْلَى أَزْهَرَ، قَالَ: صَلَّيْتُ مَعَ عَلِيٍّ بْنِ أَبِي طَالِبٍ رَضِيَ اللَّهُ عَنْهُ الْعَبْدِ وَعُثْمَانَ بْنِ عَفَّانَ رَضِيَ اللَّهُ عَنْهُ مَحْضُورًا، فَصَلَّى ثُمَّ خَطَبَ فَقَالَ: لَا تَأْكُلُوا مِنْ لُحُومِ أَضْحَائِكُمْ بَعْدَ ثَلَاثَةِ أَيَّامٍ، فَإِنَّ رَسُولَ اللَّهِ صَلَّى اللَّهُ عَلَيْهِ وَسَلَّمَ أَمَرَ بِذَلِكَ.

It was reported to us by ibn abiDaud, he said, it was reported to us by AbūSāleh, he said it was reported to me by al-Layth, he said it was reported to me by Uqayl from ibn Shahāb, he said it was reported to me by 'AbūUbaydmoulaazhar, he said, I offered Eid Prayer with Ali ibn Abi Tālib while Usmān ibn Affān (RA) was surrounded, after the prayer Ali ibn Abi Talib (d40/661)(RA) addressed, "Do not eat the meat of your sacrificial animals after three days because the order of the Apostle of Allah.

He narrated the third *Hadīth* reported by *Sālim* from his father;

حَدَّثَنَا ابْنُ أَبِي دَاوُدَ، قَالَ: ثنا يَحْيَى بْنُ صَالِحٍ الْوَحَاظِيُّ، قَالَ: ثنا إِسْحَاقُ بْنُ يَحْيَى الْكَلْبِيُّ، عَنِ الرَّهْرِيِّ، عَنْ سَالِمٍ، عَنْ أَبِيهِ، قَالَ: سَمِعْتُ رَسُولَ اللَّهِ صَلَّى اللَّهُ عَلَيْهِ وَسَلَّمَ يَقُولُ: «كُلُوا مِنْهَا ثَلَاثًا» يَعْنِي لُحُومَ الْأَضْحَى

It was reported to us by ibn Abi Daud, he said it was reported to us by Yahya ibn Sāleh al-Wahazi, he said it was reported to us by Ishāq ibn Yahya al-Kalbi from al-Zuhari from Sālim from his father, he says, "I heard the Apostle of Allah while saying, Eat from it till three (days) ie meat of the sacrificial animal.

It was reported by ibn Umar;

حَدَّثَنَا رَبِيعُ الْمُؤَدِّبِ، قَالَ: ثنا شُعَيْبُ بْنُ اللَّيْثِ، قَالَ: أَخْبَرَنَا اللَّيْثُ، عَنْ نَافِعٍ، عَنِ ابْنِ عُمَرَ، رَضِيَ اللَّهُ عَنْهُمَا، عَنْ رَسُولِ اللَّهِ صَلَّى اللَّهُ عَلَيْهِ وَسَلَّمَ أَنَّهُ كَانَ يَقُولُ: «لَا يَأْكُلُ أَحَدُكُمْ مِنْ لَحْمِ أَضْحِيَّتِهِ فَوْقَ ثَلَاثَةِ أَيَّامٍ»

"It was reported to us by Rabī' al-Moazin, he said it was reported to us by Shoab ibn Layth, he said it was reported to us by al-layth from Nāfi' from ibn Umar from the Apostle of Allah (PBUH) who used to say, "None of you should eat the meat of his sacrificial animal for more than three days.

Al-Taḥāwī argues that on the base of above mentioned *Hadīths*, it is said that it is not allowed to eat the sacrificial meat after three days of sacrifice. But on the other hand, it is said that there is no any problem in eating and saving the sacrificial meat even after three days of sacrifice on the base of the *Hadīths* in which the Prophet (PBUH) himself used the meat and also allowed others to use it after three days. For example, *al-Taḥāwī* narrated,

حَدَّثَنَا يُونُسُ قَالَ: ثنا مَعْنُ بْنُ عِيسَى: عَنْ مُعَاوِيَةَ بْنِ صَالِحٍ، عَنِ أَبِي الرَّاهِرِيِّ، عَنِ جُبَيْرِ بْنِ نُفَيْرٍ، عَنِ ثَوْبَانَ قَالَ: دَبَّحَ رَسُولُ اللَّهِ صَلَّى اللَّهُ عَلَيْهِ وَسَلَّمَ أَضْحِيَّتَهُ ثُمَّ قَالَ: " يَا ثَوْبَانُ أَسْلَحْ لَحْمَ هَذِهِ الْأَضْحِيَّةِ فَمَا زِلْتُ أَطْعِمُهُ مِنْهَا، حَتَّى قَدِمَ الْمَدِينَةَ

It was reported to us by Younas, he said it was reported to us by Ma'n ibn 'Esa from M'āwiyya ibn Sāleh from Abi al-Zahiriyya from Jubayr ibn e Nufayr from Thobn who said that the Apostle of Allah (PBUH) slaughtered

his sacrificed animal and said, “O Thobān make the meat of this sacrificed animal, (Thobān says) “I kept on serving him with that (meat) till reached Madina.”

Then *al-Taḥāwī* narrated the saying of Ayesha (RA),

حَدَّثَنَا إِبْرَاهِيمُ بْنُ مَرْزُوقٍ، قَالَ: ثنا أَبُو عَامِرٍ الْعَقَدِيُّ، قَالَ: ثنا شُعْبَةُ، عَنْ جَابِرِ بْنِ يَزِيدَ، عَنِ الشَّعْبِيِّ، عَنْ مَسْرُوقٍ، عَنْ عَائِشَةَ، رَضِيَ اللَّهُ عَنْهَا قَالَتْ: «إِنَّ كُنَّا لَنَأْكُلُهُ بَعْدَ عِشْرِينَ، نَغْنِي لُحُومَ الْأَضَاجِي»

It was reported to us by Ibrāhīm ibn Marzuq who said, it was reported to us by Abū ‘Amir al-‘Aqdī, he said it was reported to us by Sho’ba from Jabir ibn Yazīd from al-Sha’bī from Masruq from Ayesha (RA) who said “We used to eat it after twenty days i.e. meat of sacrificed animals.”

Then he narrated the saying of the Prophet (PBUH) reported by Qatada (RA):

حَدَّثَنَا إِبْرَاهِيمُ بْنُ مَرْزُوقٍ، قَالَ: ثنا أَبُو عَامِرٍ الْعَقَدِيُّ، قَالَ: ثنا زُهَيْرُ بْنُ مُحَمَّدٍ، عَنْ شَرِيكَ بْنِ أَبِي نَمِرٍ، عَنْ عَبْدِ الرَّحْمَنِ بْنِ أَبِي سَعِيدٍ الْخُدْرِيِّ، عَنْ أَبِيهِ، وَعَمِّهِ قَتَادَةَ رَضِيَ اللَّهُ عَنْهُمُ ، أَنَّ النَّبِيَّ صَلَّى اللَّهُ عَلَيْهِ وَسَلَّمَ قَالَ: «كُلُوا لُحُومَ الْأَضَاجِي وَأَدْخِرُوا»

It was reported to us by Ibrāhīm ibn Marzuq who said, it was reported to us by Abū ‘Amir al-‘Aqdī he said, it was reported to us by Zuhayr ibn Muhammad from Sharik ibn Abi Namir from ‘Abd-ur-Rehman ibn Abi Saeed al-Khudarī from his father and uncle Qatada (RA) that the Prophet (PBUH) said, “Eat the meat of sacrificial animals and preserve.

After narrating the *Hadīths* of both point of views *al-Taḥāwī* argues, “There is possibility of abrogation for any one of the both point of views. When we ponder upon, we come to know that there are other *Hadīths* which describe that first ruling has been nullified and the other has been verified.” Then he narrated the *Hadīths* describing that the ruling about not eating the sacrificial meat after three days of sacrifice was abrogated by the order of allowing to eat and store according to the need.

Al-Taḥāwī narrated eight *Hadīths* which show the abrogation in the matter under discussion, with different words and chains (*Asnād*). First, he quoted the *Hadīth* reported by Ali ibn Abi Talib (d40/661) with nine different chains that Apostle of Allah (PBUH) said,

«إِنِّي كُنْتُ نَهَيْتُكُمْ عَنْ لُحُومِ الْأَضَاجِي أَنْ تَدْخِرُوهَا فَوْقَ ثَلَاثَةِ أَيَّامٍ ، فَادْخِرُوهَا مَا بَدَا لَكُمْ»

I used to forbid you from storing the meat of sacrificial animals for more than three days, (now) you may store it as you wish.

He narrates the saying of Jabir ibn ‘Abdullah through two chains (*asnād*) that they used to eat their sacrificial animals only for three days in the era of the Apostle of Allah, then the Apostle of Allah gave them permission to eat and preserve it after that.

Then he narrated the saying of the Prophet reported by Qatada ibn No’mān,

أَنَّ رَسُولَ اللَّهِ صَلَّى اللَّهُ عَلَيْهِ وَسَلَّمَ عَامَ الْحَجِّ قَالَ: «إِنِّي كُنْتُ نَهَيْتُكُمْ أَنْ لَا تَأْكُلُوا لُحُومَ الْأَضَاجِي فَوْقَ ثَلَاثَةِ أَيَّامٍ ، وَإِنِّي أَجِلُّهُ لَكُمْ ، فَكُلُوا مِنْهُ مَا شِئْتُمْ»

That the Apostle of Allah said on the occasion of Hajj, “I used to forbid you from eating the meat of sacrificial animals for more than three days, now I make it *halāl* for you, you may eat them as long as you like.

Nubaysha al-Khayr reports that the Prophet said, “I have forbidden you from meat of sacrificial animals after three days, so Allah gave you facility now you may eat and preserve because these are the days of eating and drinking and remembering Allah.

The saying of Jabir ibn ‘Abdullāh has also been quoted by *al-Taḥāwī* that the Prophet (Peace and blessings be upon him) forbade from eating the sacrificial meat after three days, then it was allowed and the Prophet said, “Eat, give in charity and preserve”

Abū Saeed Khudri reported from the Prophet (Peace and blessings be upon him) that it was forbidden to preserve the meat of sacrificial animals for more than three days then it was allowed.

Al-Taḥāwī narrated the action of Ali ibn Abi Talib (d40/661) in the *Hadīth* reported by Ayesha (RA):

حَدَّثَنَا رَبِيعُ الْمُؤَدِّنُ، قَالَ: ثنا شُعْبَةُ بْنُ اللَّيْثِ، قَالَ ثنا اللَّيْثُ بْنُ سَعْدٍ، عَنْ يَعْقُوبَ، عَنْ يَزِيدَ بْنِ أَبِي يَزِيدَ، يَزِيدَ الْأَنْصَارِيِّ ، عَنْ امْرَأَتِهِ، أَنَّهَا سَأَلَتْ عَائِشَةَ رَضِيَ اللَّهُ عَنْهَا عَنْ لُحُومِ الْأَضَاجِي فَقَالَتْ: «قَدِمَ عَلَيَّ مِنْ أَبِي طَالِبٍ رَضِيَ اللَّهُ عَنْهُ مِنْ سَفَرٍ ، فَقَدَّمْنَا إِلَيْهِ مِنْهُ»، فَقَالَ: «لَا أَكُلُ حَتَّى أَسْأَلَ رَسُولَ اللَّهِ صَلَّى اللَّهُ عَلَيْهِ وَسَلَّمَ»، فَسَأَلَهُ فَقَالَ: «كُلُوا مِنْ ذِي الْحِجَّةِ إِلَى ذِي الْحِجَّةِ»

“It was reported to us by Rabī’ al-Moazin, he said it was reported to us by Shoayb ibn Layth, he said it was reported to us by al-Layth ibn S’ad from Yaqub from Yazīd ibn Abi Yazīd, Yazīd al-Ansari from his wife who asked Ayesha (RA) about the sacrificial meat, she (Ayesha) said, “Ali came back from his journey and we served him with the sacrificial meat but he said, “I shall not eat it until I ask the Apostle of Allah” when he asked, the prophet said, “ (You may) eat it from Zilhijjah (the month of sacrifice) to (the next month of) Zilhijjah.”

In these sayings of the companions of the Prophet (PBUH) it clears that the order of forbidding was in earlier days and after that it was allowed to store and eat the meat of sacrificed animal according to the wish of people.

Al-Taḥāwī says that

فِي هَذِهِ الْأَثَارِ مَا يَدُلُّ عَلَى نَسْخِ مَا رَوَيْنَاهُ فِي أَوَّلِ هَذَا الْبَابِ عَنْ رَسُولِ اللَّهِ صَلَّى اللَّهُ عَلَيْهِ وَسَلَّمَ مِنَ النَّهْيِ عَنْ لُحُومِ الْأَضَاجِي فَوْقَ ثَلَاثَةِ أَيَّامٍ

“These *Hadīths* are the evidence that the sayings of the Prophet (Peace and blessings be upon him) which forbid using the meat of sacrificed animal after three days, are abrogated.”

2.2.1 Answer to Objection

Al-Ṭahāwī raises a question that it has been reported in the last *Hadīth* about Ali ibn Abi Talib (d40/661) that the prophet allowed to eat the sacrificial meat during the whole year and it has also been reported about Ali ibn Abi Talib (d40/661) that he forbade the people to eat the meat after three days in the last days of Usman's era when Usman was surrounded, as quoted in the earlier lines under *al-Ṭahāwī's* discussion. So, it is possible that it was permissible to eat the sacrificial meat for more than three days and then was banned.

Al-Ṭahāwī says that this argument is not valid because it is possible that Ali ibn Abi Talib (d40/661) forbade the people from eating the sacrificial meat after three days due to some particular situation as the Prophet (PBUH) had done due to the people who had come from the villages to get meat in the days of sacrifice that has been reported by Ayesha (d58/678) in these words;

"It was reported to us by ibn Marzuq, he said, it was reported to us by AbūHuzayfa, he said, it was reported to us by Sufyān, he said it was reported to us by 'Abd-al-Rehman ibn 'Abis from his father, he said, "I came to Ayesha (RA) and asked, " O mother of the believers! Did the Apostle of Allah make it ḥarām to eat the sacrificial meat after three days? She answered, "He ordered to do so when the people were hungry in a year and he wanted to feed the poor by the rich."

Al-Ṭahāwī argues that this is an evidence that the prophet Muhammad (peace and blessings be upon him) ordered not to eat sacrificial meat after three days for a particular reason, when the situation was changed, he allowed it. Similarly, Ali (RA) ordered the people not to eat the sacrificial meat after three days, in the days of problem when Usmān (d35/656) was surrounded.

Furthermore *al-Ṭahāwī* narrates another *ḥadīth* that Ayesha (RA) says;

دَفَّ النَّاسُ مِنْ أَهْلِ الْبَادِيَةِ , فَحَضَرْتُ لِأُصْحَيَّ , فَقَالَ رَسُولُ اللَّهِ صَلَّى اللَّهُ عَلَيْهِ وَسَلَّمَ: «ادْخُرُوا التَّلْتَّ , وَتَصَدَّقُوا بِمَا بَقِيَ». قَالَتْ: فَلَمَّا كَانَ بَعْدَ ذَلِكَ قُلْتُ: يَا رَسُولَ اللَّهِ , قَدْ كَانَ النَّاسُ يَنْتَفِعُونَ بِضَخَائِبِهِمْ , يَحْمِلُونَ مِنْهَا الْوَدَكَ وَيَبْنِدُونَ مِنْهَا الْأَسْقِيَةَ. قَالَ: وَمَا ذَاكَ؟ قَالَ: نَهَيْتُ عَنْ إِمْسَاكِ لُحُومِ الْأَضَاجِيِّ بَعْدَ ثَلَاثٍ. فَقَالَ: «إِنَّمَا كُنْتُ نَهَيْتُكُمْ لِلدَّافَةِ الَّتِي دَفَّتْ , فَكُلُوا , وَتَصَدَّقُوا , وَتَرَوْدُوا»

A group of people came from the village, I slaughtered my animal, the Apostle of Allah said, "Take one third (of the animal) and give the rest of in charity." The next year I told the Apostle of Allah that the people were getting benefits from their sacrificed animals, getting fat and making water skins. He said, "Then what?" He was told that he had forbidden to preserve sacrificial meat after three days. He said, "I had forbidden due to the group of the people that had come, you may eat, give in charity and preserve it."

2.2.2 Two Aspects of Ruling

Al-Ṭahāwī discusses that the *Hadīth* reported from Ayesha (RA) shows that the order of forbidding eating sacrificial meat was not to make it *ḥarām* it was only to inspire the people to give it to the needy. He narrates;

حَدَّثَنَا فَهْدٌ، قَالَ: ثنا أَبُو حَسَانَ، قَالَ: ثنا إِسْرَائِيلُ، عَنْ أَبِي إِسْحَاقَ، عَنْ عَابِسِ بْنِ رَبِيعَةَ، قَالَ: أَتَيْتُ عَائِشَةَ رَضِيَ اللَّهُ عَنْهَا فَقُلْتُ: يَا أُمَّ الْمُؤْمِنِينَ ، أَكَانَ رَسُولُ اللَّهِ صَلَّى اللَّهُ عَلَيْهِ وَسَلَّمَ حَرَّمَ لُحُومَ الْأَضَاجِيِّ فَوْقَ ثَلَاثٍ؟ فَقَالَتْ: «لَا ، وَلَكِنَّهُ لَمْ يَكُنْ صَحَى مِنْهُمْ إِلَّا قَلِيلًا ، فَفَعَلَ ذَلِكَ ، لِيُطْعَمَ مَنْ صَحَى مِنْهُمْ مَنْ لَمْ يُصَحَّ»

It was reported to us by Fahad, he said, it was reported to us by Abū Hassan, he said it was reported to us by Israel from Abi Ishāq from 'Abisibn Rabi'a, he said, "I came to Ayesha (RA) and asked, 'O mother of Believers! Did the Apostle of Allah make sacrificial meat Ḥarām (to use it) after three days?' She said, 'No, he ordered to do so to feed the people who had not slaughtered, by the other who slaughtered their sacrificial animals'.

According to *Al-Ṭahāwī* there are two aspects of the ruling for prohibiting from eating sacrificial meat after three days. If the ruling was only to inspire the people to give meat of sacrifice in charity then there is no any problem to preserve it after the three days. If the ruling was to declare eating the meat *Ḥarām* then it would be the abrogation as the *Hadīths* have been mentioned earlier.

2. Comparative Analysis

Al-Shāfi'ī	Al-Ṭahāwī
He narrated three <i>Hadīths</i> and two verses concerning this issue.	He narrated twenty <i>Hadīths</i> with thirty chains describing this issue.
The ruling about not to eat the sacrificial meat after three days was not mandatory. It was for a particular situation.	The ruling about not to eat the meat after three days of sacrifice was to inspire the people on charity or to declare its usage <i>Ḥarām</i> after three days.
He did not declare the <i>Hadīths</i> abrogated.	He declared the ruling abrogated with one condition.
He considered the sacrifice as an optional practice not mandatory.	He considered the sacrifice mandatory for the man who is wealthy.
He described how to distribute the sacrificial meat.	He did not discuss anything about it.
He used Qurānic verses to support his point of view.	He discussed only <i>Hadīths</i> in this issue.
His method of description is rather complicated.	His method of description is systematic and easy because he puts all <i>Hadīths</i> in sequence.
He mentioned extra arguments related to the issue.	His discussion is to the point.

3. Conclusion

In the light of above discussion, it can be concluded that both the scholars *al-Shāfi* and *al-Ṭahāwī* agreed that the meat of sacrificed animals can be used after three days of sacrifice (*Eid al-Adhā*). But both the scholars discuss the contradicting *Hadīths* in different perspectives. According to *al-Shāfi* the forbidding from storing the meat of sacrificed animal was not mandatory, it was optional and he argued with quranic verses clarifying the orders that are not considered mandatory. So, the ruling of the Prophet Muhammad (peace and blessings of Allah be upon him) about not to store the sacrificial meat was not to be followed compulsorily. It has been described in the *Hadīths* narrated earlier by *al-Shāfi*.

On the other hand, *al-Ṭahāwī* described that the order of forbidding to store meat for more than three days has two aspects. It was only to inspire the people to help the needy so there is no problem in eating it after three days. But if the ruling was given to make it *Harām* and later on it was withheld and abrogated so, it can be used after three days of sacrifice.

We can say that both the scholars have same point of view about the issue but have different perspectives in resolving the contradiction. *Al Shāfi* does not consider it contradictory and *al-Ṭahāwī* addresses it as abrogation as well as temporary order according to the need and content.

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